

ISic3461

I.Sicily inscription 3461

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (Luna)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Unknown

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337428

1. [□ ἐν]θάδε κῆτε ὦ ἐν μακαρία
2. [μ]νήμη Γρηγόριος υἱὸς Πο-
3. [— —]του πρ (εσ) β (ύτερος) ζήσας ἔτη κβ·
4. [τελ]ευτᾷ δὲ ἐν Κ (υρί) ω μνηνῆ Ἰου-
5. [λίω] ²⁷Ἰου | [νίω] ²⁷ ἰνδ (ικτιῶνος) η'.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644938

PHI 337428

Bibliography

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Rizzone, V.G. 2009. Iscrizioni tardoantiche da Mineo (CT). *Epigraphica.* 71: 426-437. At 427-431 fig.2

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